

Innovative Governance Strategy: Improving Community Welfare Through Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Programs

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Abstract

This study examines the innovative strategies implemented by the West Sumbawa Regency Government in improving community welfare through the Regional Empowerment Program for Mutual Cooperation, focusing on case studies in Seloto Village, Taliwang District, West Sumbawa Regency. This study aimed to analyze the effectiveness and impact of these innovative strategies in improving the welfare of village communities. This research method uses a mixed approach method that combines quantitative and qualitative analysis. Quantitative data were collected through questionnaires to village communities to measure the impact and effectiveness of the program. In contrast, qualitative data were obtained through in-depth interviews and observations to understand community perceptions, experiences, and program implementation. The study results indicate that the government's innovative strategies, including community involvement in program planning and implementation and local capacity development, have significantly contributed to improving welfare in Seloto Village. With the implementation of the intended program, it is evident from what is expected to run according to the wishes of the government, and obstacles in its implementation can be resolved together through meetings held with existing teams.

Keywords: Community Welfare, Empowerment of Mutual Cooperation, Strategy

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Introduction

Indonesia implements a regional autonomy system, which allows local governments to organize and manage their households within the limits determined by law. Law Number 23 of 2014 regulates this regional autonomy system concerning regional government (Paunović et al., 2022). Regional Autonomy allows regional governments to decide on development and public services based on local needs. This law aims to increase community participation in decision-making, accelerate regional development, and ensure the welfare of local communities (Jansen & Kalas, 2020). Regional regulations regarding Autonomy are also contained in the 1945 Constitution in Article 18, paragraph 6, which states that regional governments have the right to establish regional regulations and other regulations to carry out autonomy and assistance duties. Regional Autonomy necessitates decentralization (Cicognani et al., 2020). Decentralization is the transfer of authority from the central government to regional governments to manage their households based on the initiatives and aspirations of their people (Wisnumurti et al., 2020).

Community empowerment is an effort or process to increase people's awareness, desire, and ability to recognize, handle, maintain, protect, and improve their welfare (Yudarwati & Gregory, 2022). Community empowerment is a non-constructive effort that facilitates increasing community knowledge and ability to identify, plan, and solve problems by utilizing local potential and existing facilities from cross-sector agencies, NGOs, and community leaders (Issundari, 2024).

Cooperation is a real manifestation of culture, emerging from society's social interactions, and is a need for humans and individuals. Social interaction is very important for human life, and cooperation must be maintained because it has a positive impact (Sukhova et al., 2022). Rahman, in cooperation, has a positive attitude that supports village development and also needs to be kept as an embodiment of the habit of working together. Amid a lack of concept experience in implementing development based on cooperation in the implementation of development and governance in the region, the Regent of West Sumbawa, Dr. Ir. H. W. Musyafirin MM. Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program. PDPGR places regional development implementation as being implemented by the regional government and the community. The regional development policy innovation Gotong Royong is the chosen approach. The basis for this development is based on considerations, including the following: First, cooperation is an entity of the Indonesian nation. Second, cooperation is needed in Indonesian society, including the needs of the people in West Sumbawa Regency. Third, in almost all regions in Indonesia, there is a tradition of cooperation, including in West Sumbawa Regency (Kurniawan et al., 2023).

In the Regional Regulation of West Sumbawa Regency Number 1 of 2021, as an amendment to Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2016 concerning the Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program, the West Sumbawa Regency Government added a clause regarding innovation, one of the principles of the Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program is Aspirational (Yohanes et al., 2023). This principle is implemented through the Andalan Equal Inclusive Service Forum (Yasinan) innovation. The Yasinan Forum is one of the new public service behaviors in West Sumbawa Regency (Wahyuningtyas et al., 2023). From this forum, officials as public servants began to hear and follow up on problems and aspirations. The solution also uses the community's perspective as a reference and is no longer based on a bureaucrat's approach. Information from 2023

BPS data regarding the high poverty rate shows that 20% of the Seloto Village population still lives below the poverty line. With a lack of job opportunities, the unemployment rate in Seloto Village reaches 10%. Low level of education: the average education level of Seloto Village residents is only eight years. Limited access to basic services: many people in Seloto Village do not have adequate access to basic services such as clean water and sanitation. The number of Mutual Cooperation Agents (AGR) in Taliwang District in 2024 currently reaches 206 AGR from 700 AGR; Taliwang District occupies First place; the highest number of AGRs is in West Sumbawa Regency. From the description above, the author wants to know the West Sumbawa Regency Government's innovative strategy in empowering the community and supporting and inhibiting factors to improve community welfare through the regional cooperation empowerment program. Therefore, researchers focus on the Government's Innovative Strategy, Improving Community Welfare Through the Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program to fill the knowledge gap.

Research Methods

Quantitative Research is a research method that combines or connects quantitative and qualitative methods (Zitri Ilham et al., 2024). This approach involves philosophical ideas, application approaches. qualitative and quantitative, as well as a combination of both in one research (Kurniawan et al., 2023). The aim of the combined quantitative-qualitative research method is to achieve better research results than using only one approach (for example, a quantitative or qualitative approach only) (Wang & Ran, 2023). This method focuses on data collection and analysis and combines quantitative and qualitative data. This research uses quantitative data to find out whether the strategy of the Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program in Seloto Village has changed from the previous year (Sukhova et al., 2022). Community members around Seloto Village were given questionnaires to obtain quantitative data, while qualitative data shows the factors that influence the government and the community around Seloto Village in improving community welfare. Offline, interviews are conducted directly (Avelino et al., 2020). Data Collection Techniques: Researchers can collect data in this research by distributing questionnaires or measuring scales. The distributed questionnaires are used by researchers as a starting point for creating instruments consisting of questions or statements. Each instrument item has a score from very positive to very negative, which can be represented by words such as strongly agree, agree, somewhat agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. This research was created in checklist form, so participants only need to put a mark (√) in the column of their choice. In quantitative analysis, a score calculation, which allows each item in the tool, to be assigned a score. Meanwhile, qualitative data collection techniques include observation, interviews, and documentation. The data analysis technique in this research is data reduction, data presentation, and concluding, while the data analysis technique uses quantitative methods using regression.

Results and Discussion

Innovative Strategy of PDPGR in West Sumbawa Regency

The West Sumbawa Regency Government has established the Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program as the main regional program through Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2016, which was later changed to Regional Regulation Number 1 of 2021 concerning PDPGR, article 1 paragraph 7 Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program, which is then abbreviated as PDPGR is regional innovation program which aims to improve the quality of community welfare in an equitable, just and sustainable manner which is implemented through structured, systematic and massive cooperation with a sincere, honest and serious spirit in carrying out services, empowerment and community development. This aligns with its mission to improve the welfare of the community in West Sumbawa Regency through cooperation empowerment and its vision to become an advanced, independent, and prosperous district with empowered communities and a culture of cooperation, especially in Seloto Village (Hasanah et al., 2023). The aim is to reduce poverty levels, improve people's living standards, increase community participation in development, and preserve the cultural values of cooperation—Regional Regulation No. 1 of 2021. The cooperation empowerment program in this era of globalization certainly presents a big challenge to the government, starting with looking at the real conditions of ecological, economic, political, social, and cultural instability, environmental degradation, and economic and political exploitation. This challenge will encourage the government to create a policy or program that can be right on target based on the conditions and problems in society. So, it is not surprising that this empowerment cannot be achieved instantly but rather through a process that is not short. The Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program must require the widest possible role of the community, not just one organizational institution, including individuals, families, religious organizations, social organizations, non-governmental organizations, and professional organizations, to implement a targeted, integrated, and sustainable program. Mutual Cooperation Empowerment is carried out by the Government, Regional Government, and the community in the form of social services to meet the basic needs of each community. Full awareness from the community greatly influences the success of PDPGR.

Table 2. Forms of Activities Realized

No.	PDPGR Activities	Target	Realization	%
1	Latrines	29 houses	Realized	29 houses
2	Rehabilitasi RTLH	10 KK	Realized	10 KK
3	Farmer's Barrier	17 Group	Realized	17 Group
4	Disability Pariri	26 person	Realized	26 person
5	Senior Citizens' Pariri	41 person	Realized	41 person

Source: PDPGR Agent Seloto Village 2024

From Table 2, in the PDPGR activity report, all targets have been successfully realized. Latrines for 29 houses have been fully implemented with results according to target. RTLH rehabilitation also achieved the target, with ten families receiving assistance. The Bariri Tani program was successful with the formation of 17 farmer groups. For the Pariri Disability and Pariri Elderly programs, 26

people and 41 people, respectively, received benefits according to the targets set. In other words, each activity achieved 100% of the targets that had been set. Top of Form Bottom of Form, The results of the interview conducted by the researcher with the Head of Seloto Village, Mr. Jalaluddin, on that occasion, conveyed that PDPGR has structured management starting from village level agents to sub-district level agents, especially Seloto village has two peliuk and six coordinators, including peliuk harapan kita satu, peliuk harapan kita dua, which play a role in facilitating planning and implementation and accountability in carrying out independent cooperation activities, cooperation stimulants, and cash-intensive cooperation together with the Community (Zitri et al., 2024).

Validity and Reliability Test

In this study, the number of respondents (n) was 30 with an alpha of 0.05, so the table was 0.340. A questionnaire is valid if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ and the sig value $\leq \alpha$. Validity test of the two variables used in this study, namely community welfare, the role of PDPGR (Sukhova et al., 2022).

Table 3. Community Welfare Validity Test

The Role of PDPGR	rhitung	rtablel	Sig	Decision
PDGR 1	0.95	0.34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 2	0.91	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 3	0.87	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 4	0.87	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 5	0.78	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 6	0.90	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 7	0.94	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 8	0.85	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 9	0.77	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 10	0.77	0,34	0.00	Valid

Source: Primary data processed June 2024

The results of the PDPGR Role validity test show the following. PDGR Indicator 1 has a calculated r value of 0.95, much higher than the r table of 0.34, and a Sig value of 0.00. This shows that the validity indicators are very strong. PDGR 2, showing a calculated r value of 0.91, also far exceeds the r table of 0.34, with the same Sig value of 0.00, confirming its strong validity. Indicator 3 and Indicator 4 have a calculated r value of 0.87, which is greater than the r table of 0.34, and a Sig value of 0.00, which shows that these two indicators are valid with a consistent level of validity. PDGR 5 has a calculated r value of 0.78, which is higher than the r table of 0.34, and a Sig value of 0.00, indicating the validity of this indicator. PDGR 6, with a calculated r value of 0.90, which exceeds the r table of 0.34 and a Sig value of 0.00, shows that this indicator is very valid. PDGR 7 shows a calculated r value of 0.94, which is also much higher than the table r of 0.34 and Sig value of 0.00, confirming its validity. PDGR 8, with a calculated r value of 0.85 higher than the r table of 0.34 and a significant Sig value, shows that this indicator is valid. PDGR 9 has a calculated r value of 0.77 and a Sig value of 0.00, which shows good validity. PDGR 10, with a computed r value of 0.77, which exceeds the r table of 0.34, and a Sig value of 0.00, also shows validity.

Thus, all tested indicators show that their calculated r values consistently exceed the table r values and have significant Sig values. Overall, this indicates that all indicators in this research are valid. This validity ensures that the instruments used in this research can be relied upon to accurately measure the variables in question and the research objectives. The strength of validity of each indicator confirms that the research instruments used meet the validity criteria needed to guarantee the accuracy and credibility of research results (Dhewanto et al., 2020).

Table 4. PDPGR Role Validity Test

QUESTION ITEM	Rhitung	rtabel 5% (30)	Sig	Decision
PDGR 1	0,80	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 2	0,92	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 3	0,91	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 4	0,91	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 5	0,97	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 6	0,82	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 7	0,92	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 8	0,70	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 9	0,57	0,34	0.00	Valid
PDGR 10	0,42	0,34	0,01	Valid

Source: Primary data processed June 2024

The PDPGR Role validity test results show PDGR 1, showing a calculated r value of 0.80, which far exceeds the r table of 0.34 and is supported by a Significance (Sig) value of 0.00. This confirms that this indicator is valid and can be used to measure the variable in question. PDGR 2 has a calculated r value of 0.92, which is also far above the r table of 0.34 with a Sig value of 0.00. The validity of this indicator is very strong, showing that indicator two effectively measures the targeted aspect. PDGR 3 and Indicator 4 each have a calculated r value of 0.91, which exceeds the r table of 0.34, and a Sig value of 0.00. These two indicators are declared valid with a high level of validity, which shows that they are reliable for research. Indicator 5 has the highest calculated r value, namely 0.97, much higher than the r table of 0.34, and a Sig value of 0.00. This shows that indicator 5 has very strong validity and is a very effective indicator to use in measurement. Indicator 6, with a calculated r value of 0.82, which also exceeds the r table of 0.34 and a Sig value of 0.00, shows that this indicator is valid and can be used in this research with good reliability. Indicator 7 shows a

calculated r value of 0.92, much higher than the r table of 0.34 with a Sig value of 0.00. The validity of PDGR 7 is very strong, confirming its reliability for measuring the variables in question. Indicator 8 has a calculated r value of 0.70, which, although the lowest value among the indicators tested, still exceeds the r table of 0.34 and is supported by a Sig value of 0.00. This shows that indicator 8 remains valid and effective for use in measurement. PDGR 9, with a calculated r value of 0.57 and a Sig value of 0.00, which also exceeds the r table of 0.34, shows that this indicator is valid and reliable in the context of this research. PDGR 10 has a calculated r value of 0.42, which exceeds the r table of 0.34 and is supported by a Sig value of 0.01. Even though the calculated r-value is relatively lower, this indicator is still valid for use in research.

Overall, all the indicators tested show that their calculated r value far exceeds the table r value, and the Significance value (Sig) shows high significance ($p < 0.05$). This confirms that all the indicators used in this research are valid; each indicator effectively measures the variables studied projectively. The strong validity of these indicators provides confidence that the research instruments used are reliable and the results obtained from this research reflect the variables analyzed accurately and credibly. Thus, the results of this research are valid and suitable for decision-making or further study.

Reliability Test

Reliability is to find out how far the measurement results remain consistent; if measurements are taken twice or more, the same symptoms are using the same measuring instrument. In this study, the reliability test used the Cronbach Alpha method. With the criteria that the calculated alpha level is greater than the Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.7, the data tested has good reliability. The output results are as follows:

Table 5. Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.936	.937	10

Source: Data processed using SPSS

Based on the reliability test results presented, the following information was obtained regarding Cronbach's Alpha coefficient: Cronbach's Alpha is known to be 0.936. Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items is known to be 0.937. Number of Items 10 The reliability test results show a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.936. This indicates that the instrument used in this study is very reliable. With this value, it can be concluded that the items in this research instrument provide confidence that the data collected is stable and can be trusted for further analysis or decision-making.

Table 6. Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.961	.962	10

Source : Data processed through SPSS

Based on the results of the reliability test presented, here are the details and interpretations of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. Cronbach's Alpha is known to be 0.961. Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items is known to be 0.962. Number of Items 10. The results of this reliability test show a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.961 and an alpha value based on standardized items of 0.962. This value indicates a very high internal consistency of the instrument used in the study. Cronbach's Alpha, which is in the range of 0.90 to 1.00, means that the items in the instrument suggest that this study has very good reliability. This high internal consistency provides confidence that the instrument can produce stable and reliable results when measuring the variables studied. Thus, this instrument can be trusted for further data analysis or making decisions based on the data collected.

Simple Linear Regression Test

Decision making in a simple linear regression test can refer to two things, namely Comparing the significance value with a probability value of 0.05. If the significance value is <0.05, it means that the Role of PDPGR has an effect on Community Welfare, If the significance value is >0.05, it means that the Role of PDPGR has no effect on Community Welfare.

Table 7. Simple Linear Regression Test

ANOVA		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Significance
Regression	1	406.37	1	406.37	18.1790	<.001b
Residual	28	62.591	28	2.235		
Total	29	468.96	29			

a. Dependent Variable: Public welfare

b. Predictors: (Constant), Role_PDPGR

Source: processed by researchers

Based on the results of the ANOVA test presented in the following table, it can be analyzed as follows: The Regression Sum of Squares is 406,375, which shows the variation in the dependent variable (Community Welfare) that can be explained by the regression model involving the independent variable (Role of PDPGR). Degrees of Freedom (df) is 1, reflecting the number of independent variables in the model. The Residual df is 28, which is the remaining degrees of freedom after accounting for the independent variables. The Total df is 29, which corresponds to the total number of observations minus one. The Regression Mean Square is 406,375, which measures the variation explained by the model per degree of freedom of the model. The F-statistic value is 181,790, which shows the comparison between the variation explained by the model and the variation not explained by the model. The very small Significance (Sig.) Value (<0.001) indicates that the overall regression model is significant at the 5% significance level.

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion, the researchers drew the following conclusions. The Regional Mutual Cooperation Empowerment Program (PDPGR) implemented by the West Sumbawa Regency Government was running well and significantly impacted the welfare of the Seloto Village community. The role of PDPGR for all indicators is optimal in improving community welfare (SS+S=97%). The role of PDPGR for all indicators has a very positive impact on community welfare (SS+S=97%). The community's active participation determines the empowerment program's success in Seloto Village, the ability of the local government to manage the program, and an effective evaluation and monitoring system. Good coordination and open communication between all parties ensure the program can adapt and achieve its goals effectively.

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References

- Avelino, F., Dumitru, A., Cipolla, C., Kunze, I., & Wittmayer, J. (2020). Translocal empowerment in transformative social innovation networks. *European Planning Studies*, 28(5), 955–977. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2019.1578339>
- Cicognani, E., Albanesi, C., Valletta, L., & Prati, G. (2020). Quality of collaboration within health promotion partnerships: Impact on sense of community, empowerment, and perceived projects' outcomes. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 48(2), 323–336. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcop.22254>
- Dhewanto, W., Ratnaningtyas, S., Permatasari, A., Anggadwita, G., & Prasetio, E. A. (2020). Rural

- entrepreneurship: Towards collaborative participative models for economic sustainability. In *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues* (Vol. 8, Issue 1, pp. 705–724). jssidoi.org. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.8.1\(48\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.8.1(48))
- Hasanah, S., Pratama, I. N., Rahmat, A. F., & Kurniawan, C. (2023). Digital Government in Social Sciences Discipline: Mapping Pivotal Features and Proposed Theoretical Model. *Jurnal Ilmiah Peuradeun*, 11(1), 195–220. <https://doi.org/10.26811/peuradeun.v11i1.819>
- Issundari, S. (2024). Decentralised International Cooperation: Insights from the Yogyakarta (Indonesia)-Gyeongsangbukdo (South Korea) Partnership. *SINERGI: Journal of Strategic Studies & International ...*. <https://sinergiukm.my/jou/index.php/sei/article/view/84>
- Jansen, L. J. M., & Kalas, P. P. (2020). Improving governance of tenure in policy and practice: a conceptual basis to analyze multi-stakeholder partnerships for multi-stakeholder transformative governance illustrated with an example from south africa. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)* (Vol. 12, Issue 23, pp. 1–30). mdpi.com. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12239901>
- Kurniawan, C., Pribadi, U., & Iqbal, M. (2023). the Role of E-Governance in Improving Local Governments Performance (Case Study: Sumbawa Regency). *Jurnal Ilmiah Peuradeun*, 11(3), 1139–1154. <https://doi.org/10.26811/peuradeun.v11i3.795>
- Paunović, I., Müller, C., & Deimel, K. (2022). Building a Culture of Entrepreneurial Initiative in Rural Regions Based on Sustainable Development Goals: A Case Study of University of Applied Sciences–Municipality Innovation Partnership. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)* (Vol. 14, Issue 19). mdpi.com. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912108>
- Sukhova, K., Borodin, Y., Tarasenko, T., Komarova, K., & ... (2022). *Organizational mechanism of state management of social services in territorial communities*. ir.nmu.org.ua. <https://ir.nmu.org.ua/handle/123456789/162936>
- Wahyuningtyas, R., Disastra, G., & Rismayani, R. (2023). Toward cooperative competitiveness for community development in Economic Society 5.0. In *Journal of Enterprising Communities* (Vol. 17, Issue 3, pp. 594–620). emerald.com. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-10-2021-0149>
- Wang, H., & Ran, B. (2023). Network governance and collaborative governance: a thematic analysis on their similarities, differences, and entanglements. *Public Management Review*, 25(6), 1187–1211. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2021.2011389>
- Wisnumurti, A. . G. O., Candranegara, I. M. W., Suryawan, D. K., & Wijaya, I. G. N. (2020). Collaborative Governance: Synergy Among the Local Government, Higher Education, and Community in Empowerment of Communities and Management of Potential Tourism Village. ... *on Business and ...*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.201116.024>
- Yohanes, Y., Elyta, E., Zulkarnaen, Z., & Kurniawan, C. (2023). Factors Affecting Community’s Intention to Use Lestari Applications Through the Umega Model. *Reformasi*, 13, 247–260. <https://jurnal.unitri.ac.id/index.php/reformasi/article/view/4935>
- Yudarwati, G. A., & Gregory, A. (2022). Improving government communication and empowering rural communities: Combining public relations and development communication approaches. *Public Relations Review*, 48(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2022.102200>
- Zitri, Rifaid, Lestanata, Y., & Kurniawan, C. (2024). Navigating digital tourism governance: a case study of branding strategies in the Mandalika special economic zones. *OTORITAS : Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan*, 44(8), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1751-8113/44/8/085201>